

The Efficacy of E-Governance in Implementing Local Economic Development (LED)

Maela Khutso Delphus

Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

E-governance (online governance) has become vital in promoting Local Economic Development (LED), especially in a world increasingly driven by technology, digital transformation, and data-driven decision-making. Through New Public Management theory, this paper seeks to probe the importance of E-governance in facilitating LED implementation. The paper theoretically investigates the challenges encountered in LED implementation and calls for e-governance for resolution. Moreover, this paper seeks to encourage and compel the policymakers or legislative authorities in South Africa to consider the effective implementation of online governance for effective LED. The contribution of "The Efficacy of E-Governance in LED at both global and national levels can be understood through its impact on policy development, capacity building, knowledge dissemination, and innovation in governance. This paper is conceptual, and it heavily relies on secondary data. Through exclusion criteria for literature, this paper examines the efficacy of e-governance in the implementation of LED. The qualitative research method will support the paper by gathering the existing information related to the topic. In probing LED, this paper found that e-governance plays a vital role in facilitating the implementation of LED. E-governance supports SDG Goal 16 (Peace, Justice, & Strong Institutions) by promoting transparency and effective governance. The paper recommends that the state have the administrative capacity, participation tools, and public-private partnerships to enhance local economic development effectively.

Keywords: Local economic development, governance, e-governance, development, economy

This paper aims to examine the efficacy of e-governance in implementing Local Economic Development. The study further seeks to address the problem that was faced by the LED in the traditional public administration. Through the New Public Management theory, this study suggests the usage of e-governance to maintain and implement LED in South African local municipalities. Local economic development (LED) as a development strategy has, in the recent past, gained widespread popularity and acceptance as a grassroots-based approach, especially in the developing world. E-governance is a powerful catalyst for improving service delivery, fostering investment, promoting transparency, and enhancing citizen participation (Nkgapele, 2024). Jakoet-Salie (2023:1) asserts that as technology advances, the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, emphasizes that the government's use of the universal electronic government (e-government) model to provide services largely depends on the country's adoption of electronic initiatives. While challenges such as the digital divide, resistance to change, and cybersecurity risks exist, they can be mitigated through strategic investment, capacity building, and inclusive governance practices. A well-implemented e-governance can stimulate vibrant, inclusive, and sustainable local economies.

According to Mashabela (2020:14), Local Economic Development

(LED) is described as a national policy initiative aimed at promoting economic growth by encouraging collaboration among local communities and stakeholders to achieve sustainable development. Similarly, Mabunda and Ndou (2019:347) explain LED as a cooperative effort where people from different sectors work together to boost local business activity, ultimately leading to a more resilient and sustainable economy. Shilangu (2019:632) emphasizes that LED is often seen as a key solution to the ongoing challenges of unemployment, poverty, and inequality within South African municipalities.

However, despite the potential of LED, local governments in South Africa face serious challenges. These include high levels of poverty and unemployment, inadequate service delivery, sluggish local economies, a shortage of skills necessary to drive LED forward, weak administrative capacity, and poor policy implementation (Munzhedzi & Phago, 2020).

The Constitution of South Africa (1996), along with the White Paper on Local Government (1998), outlines the responsibility of municipalities to actively promote both social and economic development. These frameworks emphasize the importance of LED, urging municipalities to take the lead in creating job opportunities and tackling poverty in their communities.

New Public Management: Theoretical Perspective

This paper is grounded in the New Public Management (NPM) theory. As explained by Chadwick (2023) the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in government was first introduced as a scientific idea in administrative practices during the 1950s and 1960s. Over time, especially with the rise of the internet in the 1990s, the concept evolved into what is now known as e-government, a reform trend aligned with both New Public

Author Note

Dr. Maela Khutso Delphus, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to

Dr. Maela Khutso Delphus, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, South Africa

E-mail: khutso.maela@univen.ac.za

Management and Post-NPM movements. This digital transformation first gained momentum in the United States and Europe, and later extended to parts of Asia and Africa (Chadwick, 2023). Serpa and Ferreira (2019) describe NPM as a results-driven public management model that prioritizes accountability and performance over rigid bureaucratic procedures. Supporting this, Nghonyama, Mahole, and Maela (2024:2465) observe that governments at all levels have embraced NPM to accelerate service delivery and simplify administrative functions. Indahsari and Raharja (2020) further define NPM as a management approach widely used in public sector institutions, both locally and nationally, to enhance operational efficiency.

Broadly, NPM is seen as an administrative reform model that borrows principles from the private sector, such as efficiency, innovation, and performance management, to improve the functioning of public institutions. Rather than focusing solely on policy formulation, it emphasizes measurable outcomes and service delivery quality (Ryklief & Tengeh, 2022). This shift became particularly relevant as public sector organizations came under fire for being inefficient, outdated, and slow to innovate. As Wicaksono (2019) explains, NPM ties closely to public sector innovation, which involves introducing practical changes in services, processes, and delivery mechanisms to better serve citizens. Performance measurement is a core feature of this approach, aligning it with broader performance management goals in governance. Though NPM originally emerged in wealthier OECD nations during the 1980s, it has since gained global traction, including in developing countries, as noted by Indahsari and Raharja (2020). This global spread came in response to growing criticism of the public sector's inefficiencies. The NPM movement has been central to public sector reform, especially in promoting decentralization, modern service delivery, and stronger public accountability. It operates on the assumption that management techniques from the private sector can significantly enhance public sector performance. In this study, the principles of NPM are applied in tandem with e-governance to reshape and modernize public service delivery. The integration of digital technologies ensures that the key ideals of NPM, efficiency, transparency, accountability, and citizen-centered governance, are not just theoretical but practically implemented in public administration.

E-governance in the Realm of Public Administration

Nowadays, e-governance is regarded as the most fundamental problem in public administration and information technology (Begum, 2023; Islam & Ehsan, 2023). From a global perspective, e-governance is actively committed to utilizing technological innovations to enhance public services in both the public and private sectors. E-governance is the same as e-government in the context of public administration. This indicates that the main area of e-government is where e-governance originates. One of the main problems in defining these concepts is that they are typically explained in the context of information technology, which affects how they are perceived from the perspective of public administration. This forces Mukonza (2014: 501) to state that e-governance is a subset of e-government.

According to Bloma and Uwizeyimana (2020), e-governance is the incorporation of different stand-alone approaches among government-to-government (G2G), government-to-citizen (G2C), government-to-business (G2B), and government-to-employees

(G2E). It also includes the adoption and use of ICTs to deliver public services online to ensure interaction with multiple stakeholders. To put it another way, e-governance seeks to use ICTs to deliver governmental services to both citizens and businesses. E-governance must be described within the framework of public administration since its main target groups are the government, businesses, and individuals.

According to Fang (2023), e-government offers a major boost to progress in the twenty-first century by facilitating better, more affordable government services and improved citizen-government communication. The way e-government links people and businesses with their governments is one of its most important features. Paselle et al. (2022) assert that by lowering organizational barriers, increasing information accessibility, increasing public agency transparency, encouraging citizen participation in government, enhancing communications, and bolstering democratic processes, e-government is changing organizations.

Local Economic Development and E-governance: The Locus and Focus

This paper argues that Local Economic Development (LED) serves as the central theme (the locus), while e-governance acts as the strategic direction (the focus). The emphasis on e-governance stems from the need to find better ways of implementing LED, particularly because past efforts have often fallen short due to various governance challenges. In the South African context, LED plays a vital role in driving economic growth and improving performance at the local level. It is essentially a collaborative initiative where municipalities, businesses, and other stakeholders come together to form partnerships that stimulate economic activity and create jobs within local jurisdictions (Agbevide, 2020).

At its core, LED is driven by local actors who leverage available resources to unlock their community's economic potential. This process aims not only to improve people's livelihoods and quality of life but also to address poverty (Agbevide, 2020; Reddy, 2018). Despite support from the government, many municipalities have struggled to effectively roll out LED programs. Research attributes these shortcomings to corruption, political interference, limited capacity, and insufficient funding (Rogerson, 2019:919). Another key barrier is the lack of meaningful public participation, which undermines the success of LED initiatives.

From an ICT4D (Information and Communication Technologies for Development) perspective, e-governance offers a practical solution. All municipalities have the potential to adopt efficient e-governance systems to strengthen LED. South African municipalities can integrate e-governance into their broader development agendas by embedding digital tools into their Growth and Development Strategies (GDS) and Integrated Development Plans (IDPs) (Bridges.org, 2005). These tools would allow residents, businesses, and small enterprises to interact with local governments through a range of electronic platforms.

Abrahams and Reid (2008) point out that technologies such as telephones, computers, and broadcast media can support long-term human development and the fight against poverty. They make communication more accessible and affordable and enable faster, safer commercial transactions. In today's digital era, ICTs act as accelerators, enablers, and multipliers of development, they are essential for scaling up and linking development efforts. In the

context of governance, ICTs improve the flow of information and knowledge between government, citizens, and businesses.

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2024) emphasizes the responsibility of each country to build governance systems that uphold and advance human development. This involves ongoing public engagement, as outlined in municipal IDP community participation frameworks. Abrahams and Reid (2008) further explain that many governments globally have made significant investments in ICTs to improve how governance functions. E-governance refers to the application of ICTs in administrative processes to give citizens and communities consistent access to government information and decision-making opportunities, often at low cost.

Such digital reforms are expected to improve operational efficiency within government, enhance democratic participation, increase transparency through information sharing, and deliver better public services. Nel-Sanders and Malomane (2022) argue that if local governments invest more in ICT infrastructure and maintenance, they can better support LED efforts through digital governance. The information shared through e-municipality platforms must be relevant, user-friendly, and tailored to community needs. Using local languages and context-specific content can also improve technological adoption and help close the digital divide.

Furthermore, municipalities must ensure data privacy by securing systems against unauthorized access and leaks. When well-implemented, e-governance becomes a powerful tool in advancing LED. It improves service delivery, promotes transparency, and supports local economic growth by fostering inclusive and efficient policy processes. By embedding digital governance into LED strategies, municipalities can create a more business-friendly, investment-attractive, and citizen-centered environment.

Local Economic Development: A Perspective of South African Local Government

Before 1994, South Africa's approach to Local Economic Development (LED) was heavily influenced by a pro-market stance that prioritized the formal economy while neglecting and even suppressing the township economy (Chomane & Biljohn, 2023). This economic model largely excluded the informal sector, which dominated in townships. In response to this, post-apartheid South Africa adopted a new LED policy that recognized the country's dual economy, a system where modern, formal businesses exist alongside informal, township-based enterprises (Sekhampu, 2010:42).

The Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP), introduced in 1994, marked a turning point by shifting the focus from a market-driven approach to one that prioritizes the needs of the poor (Mahlalela, 2014:36; Van der Walldt et al., 2018:157). This policy acknowledged the realities of both the formal and informal economies and aimed to include the marginalized in development efforts.

Strydom (2016:73) highlights that LED has quickly become a crucial focus area for local development. Although several government initiatives have aimed to promote LED, many rural municipalities have struggled to drive its implementation effectively. This shortfall is reflected in ongoing challenges like high unemployment, persistent poverty, and sluggish economic progress in rural communities.

Tsheola and Mokgokong (2012:379) argue that reliable public

service delivery is a foundational element for successful LED. Communities can only thrive economically and socially when essential services are available and functioning. As further emphasized by Tsheola et al. (2012:381) for LED to truly succeed, local governments must ensure access to quality infrastructure and services, such as electricity and clean water, which are key to unlocking economic potential, especially in underdeveloped rural areas.

Impediments towards Led Services: E-governance Mobilization

Koma (2012:125) notes that local government in South Africa continues to face a range of serious challenges. These include high levels of poverty and unemployment, a shortage of the skills needed to drive local economic development (LED), weak administrative capacity, and poor implementation of policies. Similarly, Kamara (2017) points out that the underperformance of LED efforts in the country is largely due to limited resources, lack of institutional capacity, and insufficient experience within municipalities to effectively promote local development. These domestic challenges are further worsened by global forces such as rapid globalization, urbanization, technological progress, and the competitive pressures of the global economy (Koma, 2014).

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, under Section 152(1)(c), mandates municipalities to promote social and economic development. Furthermore, the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, Section 153(a) requires them to manage their planning, budgeting, and administration in a way that fosters economic growth. These constitutional provisions highlight that LED should not be treated as an add-on, but rather as an integral part of how towns and cities plan and grow. Supporting this, the Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000 (as amended) provides a legal foundation that prioritizes LED within broader development and integrated planning efforts.

According to Mashamaite and Lethoko (2018), LED is a local and territorial strategy designed to address development issues specific to the needs and interests of diverse communities and regions. The Commonwealth Local Government Forum (CLGF, 2023) echoes this by describing LED as a community-driven approach that involves local leadership working alongside various stakeholders to solve problems and improve the living conditions in their areas. This approach focuses on leveraging local resources and opportunities to uplift communities from within.

However, the South African government continues to face several pressing issues that undermine its ability to deliver effective LED services. Thusi and Selepe (2023) report ongoing problems such as corruption, financial mismanagement, and maladministration, all of which contribute to poor service delivery. Despite nearly three decades of democracy, Thusi, Mahlatse, and Matyana (2023) argue that all levels of government still struggle to provide effective LED and public services at the local level. This has led to growing frustration among residents, often expressed through service delivery protests. In a country grappling with high unemployment, the public depends heavily on government services yet many feel let down by persistent failures.

These service delivery failures are further evidenced by the poor audit outcomes consistently reported across various government departments, agencies, and municipalities. These results point to

weak governance, which in turn fuels ineffective public service delivery. As Motubatse, Ngwakwe, and Sebola (2017) stress, sound governance ensures that public funds are used wisely, resulting in improved service delivery.

On a more positive note, Bvuma and Joseph (2019) argue that digitizing government services could empower citizens and reduce both protests and corruption. Friedman (2020) adds that excessive bureaucracy in the public sector often opens the door to corrupt practices. For instance, in many rural traffic departments, acquiring something as basic as a learner's license can be a slow and frustrating experience. In some cases, individuals may resort to bribery to speed up the process, a clear obstacle to development at the local level. Shifting to digital platforms can streamline such services, reduce face-to-face interactions, and minimize the opportunity for bribery.

Galushi and Malatji (2022) found that the public generally believes that digital government has the potential to reduce corruption in public offices. In this way, e-governance becomes a valuable tool for ensuring more reliable service delivery at the community level. That said, it is important to note that traditional, paper-based systems will still have their place. Certain services may still require people to visit government offices in person. Therefore, digital government should be viewed as a complement to, not a replacement for, conventional systems.

The E-government as a Driver of the Local Economic Development Strategy and Value Outcomes in the Era of 4IR

According to Mbatha (2019), a Presidential Commission on the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) was formed in South Africa in 2019 in recognition of the importance and pressing need to incorporate 4IR into the country's public service strategy and objectives. E-government initiatives must be viewed as crucial platforms that facilitate the provision of public sector services. According to Mbatha (2019: 4-5), e-government is a collection of several public sector technology platforms used to establish and maintain governmental institutions. Additionally, these arrangements allow for the efficient, effective, and accessible delivery of services (Bwalya, 2018: 5). The provision of regular government information and transactions through electronic channels is known as e-government (Marche & McNiven in Mawela, 2015: 20). Adding to this, e-Government focuses on how ICT can assist in decision-making and policy-making processes (Mawela, 2015:20).

It delves deeper into the connection between e-governance and e-government platforms. It's critical to realize that without flexible governance, e-government platforms may lose their effectiveness. According to De Oliveira et al. (2014: 134), Governance is basically the ability of human societies to perceive, adjust, and react quickly and sustainably to changes in their surroundings. By combining agile and lean capabilities with governance capabilities, they can provide value to their core business more quickly, better, and more affordably. Furthermore, it is believed that there is still a lack of knowledge integration across disciplines in the literature theory and in defining e-government, which is restricting perspectives on the integrated public sector functioning, according to De Oliveira et al. (2014: 134). Establishing the prerequisites for creating a "systems architecture to ensure the efficient delivery of government services with transparency, reliability, and accountability" is also essential,

according to Bwalya (2018: 240).

Data Technique

This conceptual paper is heavily grounded on NPM's theory to serve as the foundation and have an influence on the findings and conclusion of the study. Therefore, the qualitative research method is consulted as the paper relies on existing literature, journals, government papers and reports. Secondary qualitative data offers detailed and nuanced understandings of human behavior, perceptions, and social interactions. It allows researchers to analyze pre-existing content from books, reports, interviews, blogs, and media without costly fieldwork (Lin, 2025). This data can be used to understand the impact of e-governance on LED, citizen participation, and public policy. While it is cost-effective and time-saving, researchers must ensure that the data is credible, relevant, and ethically sourced. Secondary qualitative data refers to non-numerical information collected, recorded, and analysed by others for purposes other than the specific research at hand. This type of data provides rich, descriptive insights into human behavior, perceptions, social processes, and cultural phenomena (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024).

Results

Emanating from the discussed literature, the study found that LED has failed previously due to several challenges under the traditional government. The findings show that e-governance considerably improves service delivery by simplifying bureaucratic processes. Online systems for company registration, taxation, and permit approvals eliminate delays and corruption, allowing local enterprises to function more efficiently. The automation of governmental services has reduced paperwork and enhanced accessibility, especially for small and medium companies (SMEs). With the findings from the Department of Home Affairs, it is evident that e-governance is responsible for effective governance. The paper discovered that e-governance promotes openness by making government data and spending reports publicly available. Financial transactions and project implementation may be tracked in real-time with digital tracking systems and e-procurement platforms, reducing the potential for corruption. Citizen participation through Internet portals has also increased government accountability for LED efforts. The study findings conclude that e-governance promotes public engagement in LED planning through e-consultations, online surveys, and digital feedback systems. This has resulted in more inclusive decision-making, which ensures that LED policies meet the demands of local communities. However, difficulties such as digital illiteracy and inadequate internet access remain impediments to full participation, especially in impoverished areas.

Lesson Learned on E-Governance in Promoting Local Economic Development: Message

This paper's literature review highlights that the world is changing and requires faster technological advancements to successfully implement LED technology. It is found that through the utilization of ICTs, e-governance enhances service delivery, calls for transparency, and inclusive community engagement. It is affirmed and imparted that the adoption of digital governance can establish inclusive and conducive environments that foster economic development and a citizen-centric approach. This innovation is capable of building environmental resilience for sustainable

development. Further lessons are on the significance of boosting business through improved service delivery. The automation of business registration, license issuance, and tax payment processes can significantly reduce inefficiencies and bureaucratic obstacles, facilitating growth for existing businesses while attracting new investments. This, in turn, leads to job creation and an expanded local tax base. Furthermore, fostering transparency and accountability is crucial for economic development. By digitizing e-governance and ensuring transparency in transactions, the potential for corruption is diminished. Investors are more likely to commit to the local economy when they have confidence that regulations are enforced fairly. Additionally, public access to government information enhances trust and empowers citizens to hold their leaders accountable. E-governance significantly enhances access to economic and market data promptly. Today, many national governments disseminate information related to infrastructure, investment opportunities, labor markets, and land use through various electronic platforms. Small businesses and entrepreneurs leverage this data to make informed decisions about where and how to invest. The local economy is directly influenced by the availability and affordability of access to such information. Additionally, the importance of widespread participation and community engagement is a crucial takeaway. Cyber tools facilitate greater public involvement in the policymaking process through online surveys, public hearings, and participatory budgeting websites. When developmental agendas are shaped by the voice of the community, funds can be allocated more effectively to projects of significant economic value.

Apart from this, e-governance also encourages the establishment of small and unorganized enterprises. Certain projects have demonstrated how e-learning websites, online trading portals, and mobile-based services can empower small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and organize the unorganized sector. Since it expands the economic base and opens opportunities for marginal communities, inclusion in this manner becomes unavoidable. Therefore, investment in ICT infrastructure and capacity-building initiatives is the central element of any effective e-governance strategy. Political will and cooperation are essential pillars of effective e-governance. Strong support from high-level government officials, active contributions from civil society, and collaborative efforts between the public and private sectors collectively foster lasting and far-reaching effects. Additionally, legal and policy frameworks must evolve to accommodate electronic governance while simultaneously safeguarding users' rights. Overall, e-governance serves as a valuable tool for promoting local economic development. It enhances service delivery, promotes transparency, facilitates informed decision-making based on evidence, and empowers both citizens and businesses. However, its future success hinges on universal access, capacity building, and sustained political commitment.

Public-private Partnership as a Model for Resolution

Public-private partnerships are gaining popularity in South Africa to improve the efficacy and efficiency of delivering goods, services, and infrastructure. This method has the potential to help local municipalities achieve the SDGs. Several variables influence the attraction of PPPs. First, they make use of the combined strengths of the public and private sectors. Public-private collaborations may leverage resources and skills, resulting in successful SDG

accomplishment. Private sectors have the expertise, tools, and creativity that governments lack (Eweje et al. 2021; Gündoğdu 2019). Second, PPPs reduce the financial and development risks involved with attaining the SDGs in local governments. As discussed by Arimoro (2020) governmental bodies may lack the financial capacity to undertake large-scale infrastructure projects. In such instances, the private sector might step in to help share the load. Thirdly, PPPs can improve public service delivery's accountability, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness. Private partners are held accountable under performance-based contracts for fulfilling predetermined criteria and efficiency benchmarks (Esposito & Dicorato, 2020). This encourages the provision of high-quality services. Additionally, PPPs have the potential to support the growth of green building projects. According to Delmon (2021), PPPs can enhance infrastructure development and service delivery, two critical facets of equitable growth. Local governments in South Africa have found that public-private partnerships are an effective strategy for tackling issues connected to the SDGs. PPPs improve local government's ability to create integrated solutions, support innovative and creative thinking, lower costs, shorten delivery times, and, in some situations, shift some risks to the private partner (Guha & Chakrabarti, 2019).

For this paper to effectively implement e-governance systems, the Policymakers in South Africa must ensure that PPP is utilized as support. The private sector should partner with the public sector to provide funding, infrastructure development, ensure inclusive participation, training of employees and community members on ICT and play an oversight role in dealing with misconduct. This will assist in job creation, provision of services, poverty reduction and addressing inequality. By enforcing such innovations, there will be effective LED in local government.

Discussion and Findings of the Study

The Effectiveness of E-governance in the Department of Home Affairs: Case Studies

With the implementation of e-governance, one of the Departments in South Africa was able to manage service delivery effectively. The Automatic Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) has been implemented by the South African Department of Home Affairs to facilitate the identification of residents for various functions, including pension payment verification, passport registration, immigration control, and election registration. This adoption of biometric data for identification verification has significantly enhanced the efficiency of these procedures, reduced paperwork and minimized errors (Department of Home Affairs, 2005). A South African identity document is not only necessary for accessing governmental services but is also essential for everyday activities such as opening a bank account. For instance, banks can now utilize biometric scanners that connect to the Home Affairs National Identification System database to verify an individual's identity through their fingerprints.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper is about e-governance as a basis for fostering LED. Through the New Public Management theory, this paper was able to give a construction of the literature review as well as the findings. This paper in the discussion detail more on the concept of e-

governance as linked to the effective implementation of LED. It was therefore important for e-governance to be discussed in the realm of public administration as the foundation. Public administration as a subfield of political science remains the foundation for e-governance and LED. The paper further indicated that the reason for the call for e-governance is the challenges brought by the implementation of LED. This was affirmed by the LED discussion in South African local government. Emanating from the literature findings, it is concluded that e-governance is extremely beneficial in advancing LED by increasing service efficiency, transparency, and corporate growth. However, for long-term deployment, governments must address digital inclusiveness, infrastructure development, and cybersecurity measures. Investing in digital literacy initiatives and developing ICT infrastructure will be critical to realizing the full advantages of e-governance for local economic growth. In recap, the paper discussed the problems associated with LED in the realm of e-governance. Due to that persisting problem, the paper suggested assistance from the PPP as a way of addressing the issues to stimulate effective LED e-governance.

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